

Voltammetric Studies on some Substituted Arenediazothioethers in Non-aqueous Medium

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Substituted arenediazothioethers are electrochemically studied in benzonitrile at a RDE. These compounds are oxidised in a single irreversible two-electron wave or in a two irreversible one-electron processes depending on the nature of substituent, leading to ring-closure at the *ortho*-position in the *N*-phenyl ring. The reduction process occurs in two irreversible one-electron transfers at the azo moiety forming the corresponding radical anion and dianion respectively. The latter abstracts two protons from the solvent to give the corresponding hydrazo compound.

The elucidation of electrode processes of the electroreduction of aromatic azo compounds at the dropping mercury electrode (DME) in aqueous media have been extensively studied¹. Recently attempts to the study the electroreduction of aromatic azo moiety in proton-free benzonitrile at the rotating disc electrode (RDE) have been reported in literature². The polarographic reduction of some arenediazothioethers³ in 40 % (by volume) ethanolic Britton-Robinson buffers at the DME has been approached. In acid media the protonated azo is electrochemically reduced in two well defined irreversible two-electron waves which were assigned for the saturation of the azo group and the reductive cleavage of the resulting hydrazo compound forming the corresponding amines. In the present work, it seemed worthwhile to investigate the redox characteristics of compounds **1a-g** in aprotic non-aqueous benzonitrile (BN) at the rotating platinum disc electrode (RDE) using different techniques, such as direct current (DC), cyclic voltammetry (CV), controlled potential coulometry (CPC) and controlled potential electrolysis (CPE).

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- | | |
|----------------------------------|-------------------------|
| 1a ; X = H | d ; X = 2-COOH |
| b ; X = 2-CH ₃ | e ; X = 2-Cl |
| c ; X = 4-CH ₃ | f ; X = Naphthyl |
| g ; X = 2-NO ₂ | |

Results and Discussion

The results of DC-voltammetry are listed in Table 1. Figs. 1 and 2 represent the DC and

Fig. 1. DC voltammogram of **1e**.

cyclic voltammograms of compound **1e** and Fig. 3 represents the cyclic voltammograms of **1g**. As revealed from the results of Table 1 and that of coulometric measurements, compounds **1a-e** behave similarly. They oxidise in a single irreversible two-electron process which is followed by a coupled chemical reaction as indicated by the absence of the reverse peak in the cyclic voltammogram (EC-mechanism). The irreversibility of the electrode process is clearly observed from the shape of the cyclic

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of **1e** : (a) oxidation and (b) reduction; scan rate = 100 mV s⁻¹.

voltammograms⁴, the slope of the logarithmic analysis curves (S) according to Tomes⁵ and the values

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of **1g** : (a) oxidation and (b) reduction; scan rate = 100 mV s⁻¹.

of $(E_{3/4}-E_{1/4})^6$ as shown in Table 1. The product of the overall oxidation reaction (1-(2'-carboxyphenyl)-5-chloro-1,2,3-benzthiadiazolium perchlorate) is electrochemically active and is reduced at very low positive potential, which is confirmed through the appearance of a reduction peak in the reverse cycle. The reduction process occurs also in a single irreversible two-electron transfer, following also the well known EC-mechanism.

TABLE 1—D.C. VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF DIFFERENT ARENEDIAZOTHIOETHERS (**1a-g**) IN BENZONITRILE (BN)

Compd no.	Process	$E_{1/2}$ mV	S^*	$(E_{3/4}-E_{1/4})$
1a	O _I	1 700	159	160
	R _I	-1 100	96	100
b	O _I	1 200	171	160
	R _I	-940	312	280
c	O _I	1 770	135	120
	O _{II}	2 210	171	160
d	R _I	-960	156	156
	O _I	1 840	68	70
e	O _{II}	2 320	185	120
	R _I	-415	122	100
f	R _{II}	-950	99	120
	O _I	2 070	143	140
g	O _{II}	2 450	185	140
	R _I	-450	217	200
f	R _{II}	-1 200	121	70
	O _I	930	166	120
g	O _{II}	1 390	127	120
	R _I	-920	149	120
g	R _{II}	-1 800	153	140
	O _I	2 130	291	150
g	R _I	-850	124	100
	R _{II}	-1 650	120	115

$$*S = dE/d \log (i_d-i)/i.$$

The presence of the methyl substituent in the *para*-position has a greater effect on the oxidation process as compared with that in *ortho*-position. Thus the single irreversible two-electron wave, revealed on oxidation of the species substituted at the *ortho*-position, was splitted into two irreversible one- electron waves leading to the formation of the same oxidation product. The reduction process was not affected.

Introduction of other substituents (**1d-f**) affected somehow the redox characteristics of these compounds.

Both oxidation and reduction main waves are splitted in two irreversible one-electron waves. The substituent will stabilise the intermediate of the first electron transfer to some extent allowing the appearance of this process as a well defined single electron wave and hence the second electron transfer will appear in a separate wave.

Finally compound **1g** (Fig. 3) with a nitro group in the *ortho*-position will be oxidised similar to compounds **1a** and **1b** in a single irreversible two-electron wave while the reduction process occurs in two-electron transfers. The first one is similar to that obtained for compounds **1a** and **1b**, while the second one is the characteristic reduction wave of the nitro group in the nitro aromatic compounds⁷.

The electrochemical oxidation process of compounds **1a**, **b** and **g** which displayed two electrons in a single irreversible process, produced the corresponding dication followed by a proton removal from the *ortho*-position of the *N*-phenyl ring resulting in the formation of the monocation. During this proton removal the sulphur atom may attach itself to the free *ortho*-position of *N*-phenyl ring leading to ring-closure and the formation of the hetero ring (cation) which is further stabilised through its combination with the perchlorate anion from the supporting electrolyte.

For the other members in which the oxidation occurs in a stepwise two one-electron transfer (Fig. 2a), the radical-cation is firstly formed (peak a) followed by the uptake of the second to form the dication (peak b) which then behaves as mentioned before. The appearance of a small peak in the reverse cycle (peak c) of the oxidation at very low positive potential is characteristic of the reduction of protons which are lost during the oxidation. This peak vanishes on addition of solid sodium carbonate⁸.

The electrochemical reduction mechanism in compounds **1a**, **b** and **c** occurs through the acceptance of two electrons in one step by the azo moiety to form the dianion. For other compounds this process occurs in two successive one-electron transfer leading to radical-anion and then the dianion. The

formed dianion would be strong enough base to abstract protons from the solvent^{8,9} to give the corresponding hydrazo compound. The effect of small quantities of water must be considered and hence very dry benzonitrile was used (< 0.4 mu water) for this work in order to ensure that, if protonation does occur, the protons come mainly from the solvent and not from the residual water. Based on the separation and identification of the electrolysis product, the redox mechanism of these compounds can be represented schematically as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

The different substituted arenediazothioethers (**1a-g**) were prepared according to reported procedure¹⁰. The products were purified by repeated crystallisation from ethanol, dried at 40° for 5 h under reduced pressure and the purity was checked by tlc. The structures of all the compounds were confirmed by satisfactory elemental analysis as well as spectral data.

Benzonitrile (BN) (Rotitainerm, West Germany) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure

from orthophosphoric acid, followed by repeated distillations from phosphorus pentoxide and finally fractional distillation from potassium metal. The supporting electrolyte, tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) (Fluka-Swiss) was recrystallised several times from ethanol-water (9 : 1, v/v) mixtures and dried under reduced pressure

The voltammetric measurements were carried out on the following apparatus : VSG 72 potential scan generator as potential source; PCA 72 C potential control amplifier (Bank Electronic Gottingen, West Germany); Servogor XY (Metrawatt, Nuringberg, West Germany), T 2201 (Hartman & Braun, Frankfurt, West Germany) digital multimeter; Coulometer (Bank Electronic Gottingen, West Germany). The rotating platinum disc electrode (RDE) was mounted to a rotating motor 750 (r.p.m.) (Metrohm, Swiss).

The uv spectra (acetone) were recorded on a Varian Super Scan 3 spectrometer in dry acetone solution, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman Acculab 6 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM-360 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The microanalyses were performed using the intermediate storage technique by the Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University.

All measurements were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in dry benzonitrile (BN) containing 0.1 *M* tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as supporting electrolyte. The voltammetric studies involved the use of DC voltammetry at RDE and CV at stationary platinum disc electrode. The number of electrons participating in each electrode process was obtained using controlled potential coulometry (CPC) at platinum sheet electrode of large surface area.

The electrode potentials were measured against saturated Ag/AgCl/Cl $^-$ (BN) electrode, which was from time to time calibrated against the redox potential of caobaltocinium/cobaltocen system¹¹. The standard potential of Ag/AgCl/Cl $^-$ (BN) electrode against the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) is -176 mV¹².

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) : CPE experiments were carried out under purified N $_2$

atmosphere at a Pt net electrode in both dry benzonitrile and acetonitrile containing 0.1 mol dm $^{-3}$ lithium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. The potential was controlled at -1.6 V and 2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl/Cl $^-$ (BN) for both reduction and oxidation respectively (i.e. on the limiting current plateau of redox waves of **1e** taken as typical representative example of the studied series (**1a-g**)). The mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer. The progress of electrolysis in both the directions was followed by recording periodically the decrease in current with time. In each case, after complete electrolysis, the cell was disconnected from the circuit and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was shaken with dry ether and the supporting electrolyte was filtered off. The ethereal layer was evaporated and the resulting crude residue was crystallised from absolute ethanol.

Reduction product of 1e : This compound was identified as 2-chlorophenylhydrazo-2-carboxyphenyl sulphide (Found : C, 52.71; H, 3.82; Cl, 11.83; N, 9.28; S, 11.03. Calcd. : C, 52.97; H, 3.73, Cl, 12.05; N, 9.51; S, 10.86%); ν_{max} 3 200-3 300 (two NH), 3500 (OH) and 1 680 cm $^{-1}$ (acidic

Fig 4 Uv spectrum of **1e** (benzene solution) (1) before electrolysis and (2) after electrolysis

C=O); $\lambda_{\max} \sim 360$ nm (presence of the azo-form; this band was absent in the spectra after the complete electrolysis indicating the production of the hydrazo form during electrolysis (Fig. 4); δ 7.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 10.0 (2H, sbr, $2 \times \text{NH}$) and 12.0 (1H, s, COOH).

Oxidation product of 1e : This compound was identified as : 1-(2'-carboxyphenyl)-5-chloro-1,2,3-benzthiadiazolium perchlorate (Found : C, 39.61; H, 2.12; Cl, 17.95; N, 7.03; S, 8.30. Calcd. : C, 39.90; H, 2.05; Cl, 18.16; N, 7.16; S, 8.18%); ν_{\max} 1 200 (ClO_4), 3 500 (OH) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (acidic C=O); δ 12.0 (1H, s, COOH) and 7.2–7.5 (7H, m, ArH).

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